

РОССИЙСКАЯ АКАДЕМИЯ НАУК
Южный научный центр

RUSSIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES
Southern Scientific Centre

Кавказский Энтомологический Бюллетень

CAUCASIAN ENTOMOLOGICAL BULLETIN

Том 20. Вып. 2

Vol. 20. Iss. 2

Ростов-на-Дону
2024

Distribution and host plants of some tephritid flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) in European Russia and Armenia

© D.A. Evstigneev¹, I.V. Kuznetsova¹, A.B. Ruchin²

¹Ulyanovsk Civil Aviation Institute, Mozhayskiy Street, 8/8, Ulyanovsk 432071 Russia. E-mail: temporaria@yandex.ru

²Joint Directorate of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve and National Park “Smolny”, Krasnaya Street, 30, Saransk, Republic of Mordovia 430005 Russia. E-mail: ruchin.alexander@gmail.com

Abstract. First records of Tephritidae spp. (Diptera) for selected areas of European Russia are presented: *Chaetostomella rossica* Hendel, 1927 for Ulyanovsk and Samara regions, *Euleia rotundiventris* (Fallén, 1814) for Ulyanovsk Region and Mordovia, *Urophora stylata* (Fabricius, 1775) for Samara Region and Mordovia. *Tephritis neesii* (Meigen, 1830) is recorded from Armenia and Transcaucasia for the first time. Two species of Asteraceae from Armenia, *Centaurea takhtajanii* Gabrieljan et Tonjan and *Psephellus pulcherrimus* (Willd.) Wagenitz, were identified as new host plants of *Acanthiophilus helianthi* (Rossi, 1794) and *Terellia odontolophi* Korneyev, 1993, respectively.

Key words: Tephritidae, first records, host plants, Russia, Armenia.

Распространение и кормовые растения некоторых мух-пестрокрылок (Diptera: Tephritidae) в Европейской России и Армении

© Д.А. Евстигнеев¹, И.В. Кузнецова¹, А.Б. Ручин²

¹Ульяновский институт гражданской авиации имени Главного маршала авиации Б.П. Бугаева, ул. Можайского, 8/8, Ульяновск 432071 Россия. E-mail: temporaria@yandex.ru

²Объединенная дирекция Мордовского государственного природного заповедника и национального парка «Смольный», ул. Красная, 30, Саранск, Республика Мордовия 430005 Россия. E-mail: ruchin.alexander@gmail.com

Резюме. Впервые для ряда регионов Европейской России приведены следующие мухи-пестрокрылки (Diptera: Tephritidae): *Chaetostomella rossica* Hendel, 1927 для Ульяновской и Самарской областей, *Euleia rotundiventris* (Fallén, 1814) для Ульяновской области и Мордовии, *Urophora stylata* (Fabricius, 1775) для Самарской области и Мордовии. Пестрокрылка *Tephritis neesii* (Meigen, 1830) впервые зарегистрирована в Армении и Закавказье. Два вида сложноцветных из Армении, *Centaurea takhtajanii* Gabrieljan et Tonjan и *Psephellus pulcherrimus* (Willd.) Wagenitz, впервые зафиксированы как кормовые растения пестрокрылок *Acanthiophilus helianthi* (Rossi, 1794) и *Terellia odontolophi* Korneyev, 1993 соответственно.

Ключевые слова: Tephritidae, первые указания, кормовые растения, Россия, Армения.

As part of the on-going study of tephritid flies in Armenia and Russia, another portion of the species has been treated. New distribution or host records are provided for several species of tephritid flies in Armenia and European Russia (Mordovia, Ulyanovsk and Samara regions).

The material was collected in 2000–2023 and it is deposited in the first author’s private collection. The comprehensive description of the methodologies including sample collection, rearing and identification is presented in preceding articles [Evstigneev, Glukhova, 2020; Evstigneev, Przhiboro, 2021 etc.]. The morphological terminology used follows the standard set in the “Glossary” chapter of the book “Fruit Flies (Tephritidae): Phylogeny and Evolution of Behavior” [White et al., 2000]. Illustrations of host plant species in habitat are provided. The host plants were identified using “Flora of Armenia” [1995] and Majeovski [2006]. For rearing capitula-infesting flies from host plants, capitula were dissected from stems and placed in cotton bags to minimise the risk of mould development and to ensure more slowly and gradual drying of the capitula tissues.

Acanthiophilus helianthi (Rossi, 1794) (Fig. 1)

Material. Armenia. 1♀, 2♂, Aragatsotn Region, near Tatul vill., subapical part of Arteni Mt., mountain steppe, 16.07.2023, reared from capitula of *Centaurea takhtajanii* Gabrieljan et Tonjan 17.07.2023 (D.A. Evstigneev).

Notes. The female wing of *A. helianthi* reared from *C. takhtajanii* (Fig. 11) is illustrated in Fig. 1. This plant species has not been previously recorded as host plant.

Distribution. Eurasia and North Africa to Ethiopia [Morgulis et al., 2015].

Chaetostomella rossica Hendel, 1927 (Fig. 2–7)

Material. Russia. 5♀, 6♂, Ulyanovsk Region, Bazarny Syzgan District, Papuzy vill., 15–30.07.2011, reared from capitula of *Jurinea cyanoides* (L.) Rchb. 1–23.08.2011 (I.V. Kuznetsova); 3♀, 2♂, Samara Region, Kinel District, near Poplavskiy settlement, disturbed sandy steppe near Lake Razreznoye, swept from *Jurinea* sp., 23.06.2018 (D.A. Evstigneev).

Notes. *Chaetostomella rossica* was originally described as *Chaetostomella onotrophes* forma *rossica* based on specimens from Sarepta (now Krasnoarmeysk District of

Figs 1–9. Tephritidae species, details of structure.

1 – *Acanthiophilus helianthi*; 2–7 – *Chaetostomella rossica*; 8 – *Euleia rotundiventris*; 9 – *Terellia odontolophi*, 1 – female wing; 2–3, 8 – female habitus; 2, 8 – lateral view, 3 – dorsal view; 4 – male abdomen, dorsal view; 5, 9 – glans of phallus; 6 – spermatheca; 7 – distal part of aculeus.

Рис. 1–9. Виды Tephritidae, детали строения.

1 – *Acanthiophilus helianthi*; 2–7 – *Chaetostomella rossica*; 8 – *Euleia rotundiventris*; 9 – *Terellia odontolophi*, 1 – крыло самки; 2–3, 8 – самка, общий вид; 2, 8 – сбоку, 3 – сверху; 4 – брюшко самца сверху; 5, 9 – гланс фаллуса; 6 – сперматека; 7 – дистальная часть акулеуса.

Volgograd). The morphological details of *Ch. rossica* of both sexes are illustrated in Figs 2–7. This species is recorded from Ulyanovsk and Samara regions for the first time.

Distribution. Germany [Korneyev, 2009], Ukraine [Korneyev, 1985a, b], Russia (Voronezh Region [Korneyev, 2003], Volgograd Region [Hendel, 1927], Ulyanovsk and Samara regions).

Euleia rotundiventris (Fallén, 1814)
(Fig. 8)

Material. Russia. 1♀, Ulyanovsk Region, Radishchevo District, natural monument “Malaya Atmala”, 9.06.2006 (D.A. Evstigneev); 1♀, Mordovia, National Park “Smolny”, cordon Novinkovskiy, 54.931°N / 43.421°E, 4–7.07.2020 (K.P. Tomkovich).

Notes. *Euleia rotundiventris* is a leaf-miner of a wide range of umbelliferous plants. The habitus of *E. rotundiventris* is illustrated in Fig. 8. This species is recorded from Ulyanovsk Region and Mordovia for the first time.

Distribution. British Isles [White, 1986, 1988], Sweden [Korneyev, 1991], Switzerland [Merz, 1994], Austria [Merz, Kofler, 2008], Hungary [Mihályi, 1959, 1960], Ukraine [Korneyev, 1987, 1991], Russia (Leningrad Region [Stackelberg, 1958], Moscow Region [Rozkov, 1956; Korneyev, 1991], Chelyabinsk Region, Bashkiria [Korneyev, 1991], Kemerovo Region [Shcherbakov, 2002], Tomsk Region [Shcherbakov, 2020], Ulyanovsk Region and Mordovia), Kazakhstan [Korneyev, 1991].

Terellia odontolophi Korneyev, 1993
(Fig. 9)

Material. Armenia. 2♀, 3♂, Aragatsotn Region, Aragats Mt., mountain side facing Arailer Mt., 16.07.2022, reared from capitula of *Psephellus pulcherrimus* (Willd.) Wagenitz 2.08.2022 (D.A. Evstigneev).

Notes. Larvae of *Terellia odontolophi* develop in the capitula of various species of the genus *Psephellus*; *P. pulcherrimus* (Fig. 10) is recorded for the first time as a host plant of *T. odontolophi*. Figure 10 shows a female of *T. odontolophi* sitting under the capitulum of *P. pulcherrimus*.

Distribution. Ukraine [Korneyev, 1993], Russia [Evstigneev, 2013], Armenia [Evstigneev, Glukhova, 2021], Iran [Zarghani et al., 2016].

Figs 10–11. Asteraceae species, host plants.
Рис. 10–11. Виды Asteraceae, кормовые растения.
10 – *Psephellus pulcherrimus*; 11 – *Centaurea takhtajanii*.

Tephritis neesii (Meigen, 1830)
(Figs 12–17)

Material. Armenia. 2♀, 3♂, Gegharkunik Region, vicinity of Sevan Town, mountain side facing Sevan Psychiatric Hospital, 24.07.2022, reared from capitula of *Leucanthemum vulgare* Lam. 4.08.2022 (D.A. Evstigneev).

Notes. *Tephritis neesii* was reared from typical host plant, namely *Leucanthemum vulgare* Lam. The morphological details of *T. neesii* of both sexes are illustrated in Figs 12–17. This species is recorded from Armenia and Transcaucasia for the first time.

Distribution. British Isles [White, 1986, 1988], Spain, Andorra [Merz, 2001], Belgium [Baugnée, 2006], Switzerland [Merz, 1994], Croatia [Kovac et al., 2022], Hungary [Mihályi, 1959], Lithuania [Lutovinovas, 2014], Ukraine [S. Korneyev, 2011], Russia (Leningrad Region [Stackelberg, 1958], Ulyanovsk Region [Evstigneev, 2016]), Armenia.

Urophora stylata (Fabricius, 1775)
(Fig. 18–22)

Material. Russia. 1♀, Mordovia, National Park “Smolny”, quarter 87, sweeping, 30.06.2021 (G.B. Semishin); 2♀, 3♂, Samara Region, Pestravka District, between nature monument “Teplovskaya Balka” and Mayskoe vill., saline saucer-shaped lowland, 13.09.2000, reared from capitula of *Cirsium esculentum* (Siev.) C.A. Mey. 2021 (V.K. Pastushkova, E.I. Pastushkov).

Notes. *Urophora stylata* is a gall-forming species associated with the capitula various species of the genus *Cirsium* [White, 1988]. The morphological details of *U. stylata* of both sexes are illustrated in Figs 18–22. This species is recorded from Samara Region and Mordovia for the first time.

Distribution. Widely distributed in the Palearctic Region [White, Korneyev, 1989].

Figs 12–22. Tephritidae species, details of structure.
12–17 – *Tephritis neesii*; 18–22 – *Urophora stylata*. 12, 19 – female wing; 13 – male head; 14 – female abdomen; 15, 22 – glans of phallus; 16 – apical and subapical parts of aculeus; 17, 21 – apex of aculeus; 18 – female habitus, lateral view; 20 – aculeus.

Рис. 12–22. Виды Tephritidae, детали строения.
12–17 – *Tephritis neesii*; 18–22 – *Urophora stylata*. 12, 19 – крыло самки; 13 – голова самца; 14 – брюшко самки; 15, 22 – гланс фаллуса; 16 – верхняя и предвершинная части акулеуса; 17, 21 – вершина акулеуса; 18 – самка, общий вид сбоку; 20 – акулеус.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to anonymous reviewer for valuable advices.

The work of A.B. Ruchin was funded by the Russian Science Foundation, grant No. 22-14-00026.

References

- Baugnée J.-Y. 2006. Contribution à la connaissance des Tephritidae de Belgique (Diptera: Brachycera). *Notes fauniques de Gembloux*. 59(2): 63–113.
- Evstigneev D.A. 2013. The first find of *Terellia odontolophi* (Diptera, Tephritidae) in Russia. *Ukrainska entomofaunistyka*. 4(1): 48 (in Russian).
- Evstigneev D.A. 2016. Tephritid flies of the “Higher Tephritines” group (Diptera, Tephritidae, Tephritinae) of Ulyanovsk and Samara regions (Russia). *Ukrainska entomofaunistyka*. 7(1): 1–29 (in Russian).
- Evstigneev D.A., Glukhova N.V. 2020. First records of two species of Tephritidae and one species of Platystomatidae (Diptera) from Transcaucasia. *Zoosystematica Rossica*. 29(1): 155–161. DOI: 10.31610/zsr/2020.29.1.155
- Evstigneev D.A., Glukhova N.V. 2021. New records of Tephritidae (Diptera) from Armenia and Russia, with new data on the host plants. *Caucasian Entomological Bulletin*. 17(2): 341–344 (in Russian). DOI: 10.23885/181433262021172-341344
- Evstigneev D.A., Przhiboro A.A. 2021. New records of flies of the genus *Tephritis* (Diptera: Tephritidae) from the Caucasus and Transcaucasia, with notes on other tephritid species. *Zoosystematica Rossica*. 30(1): 13–24. DOI: 10.31610/zsr/2021.30.1.13
- Flora of Armenia. Vol. 9. Campanulaceae, Asteraceae. 1995. Havlíčkův Brod: Koeltz Scientific Books. 675 p. (in Russian).
- Hendel F. 1927. Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region. 49. Trypetidae. Stuttgart: E. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung. 221 p., taf. I–XVII.
- Korneyev S.V. 2011. Review of fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) of Transcarpathian Region (Ukraine). *Ukrainska entomofaunistyka*. 2(4): 31–38 (in Ukrainian).
- Korneyev V.A. 1985a. Mukhi-pestrokrylki (Diptera, Tephritidae) Srednego Pridneprov'ya (s obzorom sistemy semeystva v tselom) [Tephritid flies (Diptera, Tephritidae) of the Middle Dnieper region (with a review of the family system in general). PhD Thesis]. Kiev. 470 p. (in Russian).
- Korneyev V.A. 1985b. Fruit flies of the tribe Terelliini Hendel, 1927 (Diptera, Tephritidae) of the fauna of the USSR. *Entomologicheskoe obozrenie*. 64(3): 626–644 (in Russian).
- Korneyev V.A. 1987. Little-known species of tephritid flies (Diptera, Tephritidae) of the fauna of Ukraine. In: Fauna i biotsenoticheskie svyazi nasekomykh Ukrainy [Fauna and biocenotic relationships of insects of Ukraine] Kiev: Naukova dumka: 83–87 (in Russian).
- Korneyev V.A. 1991. Tephritid flies of the genera allied to *Euleia* (Diptera, Tephritidae) of the USSR fauna. Communication 1. *Vestnik zoologii*. 3: 8–17 (in Russian).
- Korneyev V.A. 1993. A new species of *Terellia* (Diptera, Tephritidae) from Ukraine. *Zoologicheskii zhurnal*. 72(4): 144–146 (in Russian).
- Korneyev V.A. 2003. New and little-known Tephritidae (Diptera, Cyclorhapha) from Europe. *Vestnik zoologii*. 37(3): 3–12.
- Korneyev V.A. 2009. *Chaetostomella rossica* Hendel, 1927 (Diptera: Tephritidae) new to Germany and West Europe. *Mitteilungen des Entomologischen Vereins Stuttgart*. 44: 65–66.
- Kovac D., Kameneva E.P., Korneyev V.A. 2022. A review of Tephritidae and Ulidiidae (Diptera, Tephritoidea) of Croatia. *Zoodiversity*. 56(5): 349–372. DOI: 10.15407/zoo2022.05.349
- Lutovinovas E. 2014. New data on the fruit flies in Lithuania (Diptera: Tephritidae). *New and rare for Lithuania insect species*. 26: 62–72.
- Majevski P.F. 2006. Flora sredney polosy evropeyskoy chasti Rossii [Flora of the middle zone of the European part of Russia]. Moscow: KMK Scientific Press Ltd. 600 p. (in Russian).
- Merz B. 1994. Insecta Helvetica. Fauna. 10. Diptera. Tephritidae. Genève: Schweizerischen Entomologischen Gesellschaft. 198 p.
- Merz B. 2001. Faunistics of the Tephritidae (Diptera) of the Iberian Peninsula and the Balears. *Mitteilungen der Schweizerischen Entomologischen Gesellschaft*. 74: 91–98. DOI: 10.5169/seals-402800
- Merz B., Kofler A. 2008. Fruchtfliegen aus Osttirol und Kärnten (Österreich) (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Linzer biologische Beiträge*. 40(2): 1211–1224.
- Mihályi F. 1959. A revision of the trypetids of the Carpathian Basin (Diptera). *Annales historico-naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*. 51: 339–362.
- Mihályi F. 1960. Fűrőlegyek Trypetidae. *Magyarország Állatvilága*. 15(3): 1–76.
- Morgulis E., Freidberg A., Dorchin N. 2015. Phylogenetic revision of *Acanthiophilus* (Diptera: Tephritidae), with a description of three new species and a discussion of zoogeography. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*. 108(6): 1060–1087. DOI: 10.1093/aesa/sav087
- Shcherbakov M.V. 2002. Tephritid flies (Diptera, Tephritidae) from Central Kuznetsk Alatau Mountains. *Entomological Review*. 82(5): 532–557.
- Shcherbakov M.V. 2020. A review of leaf-miner tephritid flies (Diptera, Tephritidae) of the south-eastern part of West Siberia, Russia. *Acta Biologica Sibirica*. 6: 637–647. DOI: 10.3897/abs.6.e59735
- Rozkov A.S. 1956. Material on the fauna and ecology of trypetid flies (Diptera, Trypetidae) of Moscow Region. In: Trudy Vsesoyuznogo entomologicheskogo obshchestva. T. 45 [Proceedings of the All-Union Entomological Society. Vol. 45]. Moscow, Leningrad: Academy of Sciences of the USSR: 193–217 (in Russian).
- Stackelberg A.A. 1958. List of Diptera of Leningrad Region. III. Diptera Acalyptrata, part 1. In: Trudy Zoologicheskogo instituta Akademii nauk SSSR. T. 24. Materialy po izucheniyu fauny i ekologii nasekomykh Leningradskoy oblasti [Proceedings of the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR. Vol. 24. Materials on the study of the fauna and ecology of insects of Leningrad Region]. Leningrad: Academy of Sciences of the USSR: 103–191 (in Russian).
- White I.M. 1986. A new species of *Paroxyena* Hendel and notes on the nomenclature of other British Tephritidae (Diptera). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*. 122: 145–163.
- White I.M. 1988. Handbook for the identification of British Insects. Vol. 10, Part 5a. Tephritid flies. Diptera: Tephritidae. London: Royal Entomological Society. 134 p.
- White I.M., Korneyev V.A. 1989. A revision of the western Palaearctic species of *Urophora* Robineau-Desvoidy (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Systematic Entomology*. 14: 327–374. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-3113.1989.tb00289.x
- White I.M., Headrick D.H., Norrbom A.L., Carroll L.E. 2000. Chapter 33. Glossary. In: Fruit flies (Tephritidae): phylogeny and evolution of behavior. Boca Raton: CRC Press: 881–924.
- Zarghani E., Khaghaninia S., Mohamadzade Namin S., Karimpour Y., Korneyev V.A. 2016. First records of the fruit flies (Diptera, Tephritidae) in the fauna of Iran. *Vestnik zoologii*. 50(2): 123–134. DOI: 10.1515/vzoo-2016-0015

Received / Поступила: 9.08.2024

Accepted / Принята: 2.12.2024

Published online / Опубликована онлайн: 28.12.2024